

The editor's-in-chief address

Dear Reader!

I am pleased to present this year's second (and twelfth since its foundation) issue of the "Ukrainian Information Space".

It is no exaggeration to say that this publication presents the latest results of the scientific work of a select group of honest, indifferent and passionate journalism researchers from all over Ukraine. These are, first of all, those who are always in a "scientific form"; who, following the inner call of their scientific and professional conscience, have already found their topic; who can thoroughly study and present their own writing "to the people" in an original way; who are unacceptable to the approach of primitive abstracting or narrative compilation of what has already been discovered, which is still unfortunately common in our environment; who do not borrow from others but stubbornly and persistently assert their own. Of course, with the obligatory experiment of their own or with their own extracted and deeply comprehended documentary and archival component.

The problems of this issue cover virtually all facets of the journal's editorial policy, its main sections, traditionally framed in both print and electronic versions by colourful symbols-pysankas with an interpenetrating Internet serpentine. Thus, understanding the practice, theory and history of two typologically diverse strata of media: print and online in national and global contexts.

As always, the content of the first section: "Actual Issues of the Ukrainian Information Space" is in line with the current difficult challenges of practical journalism. Among some telling trends in contemporary Ukrainian journalism, one is particularly disturbing: our media continue to bear the ominous stamp of the era from which we recently came out — the totalitarian one. Newer researchers also call it post-totalitarian or post-oligarchic, which, however, reflects the persistent desire of a part of the journalistic corps, rather than the media founders, to follow the path of the free press of the West following the standards and principles established in the civilised world.

One of the sharp edges of this trend is the civic stance and morality of a modern journalist, his ability to be either upright or corrupt, to be tempted by the lure of a "money bag" or to remain faithful to the profession standards. This problem, based exclusively on archival materials, is discussed in the article "Totalitarian journalism: to the problem of buying journalists' loyalty and obedience by the authorities".

The aforementioned problem is also tangible in Oleksandr Savenko's article. It is perhaps the first scientific and practical analysis of the history of the vicissitudes surrounding the adoption by the Verkhovna Rada of

Ukraine in December 2022 of the long-awaited Law of Ukraine “On Media”. As is well known, the adoption of this law as a priority was demanded by the Council of Europe from Ukrainian legislators. The article highlights the four logically related components of the problem: the history of its adoption, its advantages, shortcomings, and warnings. The author's rhetorical question “Will the new law pose a threat to freedom of speech?” remains beyond the scope of this article and opens up another topic for current research.

In recent months, the concept of AI (artificial intelligence) has been circulating in the humanities community. A discussion of the positives and threats, including for the journalistic environment, was started in the last issue of UIS by a young researcher S. Shashenko. Today, we are continuing this promising topic. Professor Tetiana Humeniuk focused on the philosophical aspect of the problem. She offered recommendations and a framework for responsible AI development. According to the author, by adhering to ethical and legal boundaries, humanity can create a future where artificial intelligence technologies in the information space are developed, deployed and used in a way that respects human values, promotes justice and accountability, and solves societal problems. Instead, Oleksii Sytnyk, developing the topic, focuses on the technological problems of introducing AI into the practice of modern media.

Professor Valentyna Halych draws the colleagues attention to the need to address the phenomenon of national publicism in our time. After all, such texts often deal with the spiritual lessons of prominent Ukrainian political and cultural figures of the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, which can inspire contemporaries and strengthen their sense of freedom and courage in confronting the Russian aggressor. The author chose one of these examples, Oles Honchar's unpublished text “Time for Unity,” for her journalistic analysis.

The UIS editorial board has been covering the issue of “War and Journalism” since the beginning of the Russian invasion. In this issue, we have decided to highlight it in a separate section. The article by Yurii Bondar “Journalists about the Russian-Ukrainian war: issues and genre features of book publications” is fundamental. The article is exploratory and enriched with a number of illustrations. There is no doubt that the relevance of the topic and its patriotic and educational impact will only grow over time. It features a series of future creative and applied works, as well as theoretical and practical research by bachelor's and master's degree students from more than 80 departments, faculties and institutes of journalism in Ukraine.

The value of the study “The Concept of 'News' in the Perception of Ukrainians during the War” lies in the fact that it was conducted by a young researcher Myroslava Chabanenko, in frontline Zaporizhzhia. It was based on an associative experiment borrowed from psycholinguistics, and about

five hundred participants responded with real questionnaires. This is a good example for our younger generation — what topics to choose and how to fill the third, experimental part of their master's thesis.

By the way, about the choice and implementation of topics by masters-journalists. In this section, we publish two such works, both from KNUKIM. Valeriia Yarzhevska (scientific supervisor Prof. M. Tymoshyk) convincingly showed the peculiarities of the media activity in the Khmelnytskyi region during the Russian war against Ukraine, and Daryna Kolomiets (scientific supervisor Natalia Dmytrenko) — the specifics of Ukrainian radio broadcasts under the same conditions. Both authors have collected and summarised a considerable amount of empirical material, and have demonstrated their ability to analyse it and draw independent conclusions.

Now for the section on the “History of Journalism”, which is extremely relevant in terms of its importance and breadth of topics. For the first time, we present equally powerful articles by well-known researchers from the two leading Ukrainian scientific schools of press history — Kyiv and Lviv. We are talking about iconic, yet little-known, even among experts, centres of Ukrainian journalism in foreign countries — from the “Kharbinskyi Visnyk” in China (Olena Drozdovska), “Hromadska Dumka” in the German camp for Ukrainian prisoners in Wetzlar (Ihor Sribniak and Dmytro Hryn) to the legendary “Svoboda” newspaper in the United States (Serhii Kozak). The standard of scientific integrity can be considered source and historiographical research on the phenomenon of the “Notes of the Shevchenko Scientific Society” (Lidiia Snitsarchuk), the seven-volume “Ukrainian Press in Ukraine and the World in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries” (Nadiia Kulesha). As always, we find unexpected Ukrainian studies angles in Vasyl Gabor's new research. Today, we are presenting the result of his analysis of travel essays about Italy in the pages of Western Ukrainian magazines of the first third of the twentieth century.

The “Public Relations” section is represented by one article by Lviv researcher Nataliia Voitovych. The topic is highly relevant — ethical challenges of political advertising. This article, as well as the research by Tetiana Humeniuk, are addressed to English-speaking readers.

Mykola Tymoshyk,
Editor-in-Chief
of “Ukrainian Information Space”